

A Case Study: Role of *Darvyadi Lauha* in *Pandu Roga*

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ABSTRACT

Ayurvedic classics have always attempted to meet the requirement for knowledge breakthroughs in order to keep up with the demands of time. The stated goal of Ayurveda as a medical system is to help humanity live a healthier and longer life. Pandu or Anemia, is one of the most common illnesses that people face. Pandu is a disorder that causes pale discoloration of the body. Pandu Roga is a disease that is described in Ayurveda's main classical texts. Pandu Roga is a Rasa pradoshaja vikara, according to Acharya Charak. Pandu Roga was given a name according on how it was presented. The symptoms of pandu roga are similar to anemia. Anemia is a disease which is characterized by decreased hemoglobin concentration. Because Anemia is such a widespread ailment in today's culture, and the adverse effects of allopathic iron preparations, like constipation and gastrointestinal irritation, are so common, a healthier alternative, named Darvyadi Lauha, is required. Triphala, Trikatu, Daruhaldi, Vidanga and Lauhabhasama are the ingredients. These herbs function on the levels of Dosha, Dushya, Agni, and Strotas, while Lauha Bhasma has Rakta Dhatu Vardhan property.

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INTRODUCTION

Pandu Roga is a disease condition described in almost all the *Ayurveda* texts and it has a lot of similarities to Anemia's clinical presentation. Also, there are number of iron and non-iron containing preparations have been mentioned in the texts for its treatment.

In India, Nutritional Iron Deficiency is the leading cause of Anemia. It is a complex condition with many facts, *Strotas*, *Dhatu*s, and *Dosha*s, demanding a multidimensional therapy approach. Anemia is more than a mineral deficit; it involves a number of components in the absorption, conversion, and utilization of iron, with the liver playing a key role.

Pandu Roga affects a large number of people as a result of modern lifestyles, poor food habits, and routines. The time has come to seriously pursue fruitful study in conditions such as *Pandu Roga*, where *Ayurveda* can provide a better solution.

If the *Rasa Dhatu* is out of equilibrium, it might cause all of the other *Dhatu*s to be out of balance as well. *Rasa Dhatu*'s function is dependent on *Agni*; if *Agni* becomes vitiated, *Rasa Dhatu* may also become vitiated, affecting the production of *Rakta Dhatu*. This may explain why, in addition to *Panduta*, the acharyas included *Pandu* in the *Rasa Pradoshaja Vikaras*

ⁱand identified *Alpa Rakto* as a crucial aspect of the conditionⁱⁱ.

As *Agnimandya* is the root cause of *Pandu Roga*, so to correct *Pandu Roga*, it is necessary to administrate drug which has *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Anulomana*, *Yakrituttejaka* properties and *Rakta Dhatu Vardhak* properties.

Anemia affects 1.62 billion individuals worldwide (95 percent confidence interval: 1.50-1.74 billion), or 24.8 percent of the population (95 percent CI: 22.9-26.7 percent). Men had the lowest prevalence (47.4 percent, 95 percent CI: 45.7-49.1) and children have the highest prevalence (47.4 percent, 95 percent CI: 45.7-49.1). (12.7 percent, 95 percent CI: 8.6-16.9 percent)ⁱⁱⁱ

MATERIAL AND METHODS-

Case presentation-

A female patient, aged 23 years was registered from the OPD (OPD/IPD No. K-/4175/22201), Department of *Kayachikitsa*, *Rishikul Campus*, *Haridwar* on. The patient had various issues related to *Pandu Roga* including pallor, breathlessness on exertion, drowsiness, fatigue and weakness for one year and palpitation and anorexia for 3 months.

History of present illness-

According to patient, she was asymptomatic one year back, she gradually developed complaints like breathlessness on exertion, fatigue, drowsiness, weakness. On further inquiry patient said that, she also has complaint of palpitation and anorexia from past three month. The patient presented to our OPD with another problem, but after proper investigation and examination got diagnosed with *Pandu Roga*.

Past history of the patient-

There is no past history of any hospitalization/ surgery/ HTN/DM and family history was also not relevant.

General examination-

Pallor was present in palpebral conjunctiva. Pulse rate recorded as 92/min. B.P was 100/68mmHg. The body temperature recorded was 98.6^oF. No abnormalities found on examining gastrointestinal, respiratory, cardiovascular and nervous system. The prakriti of patient was diagnosed as *Pittavataja* and *Nadi* was *Vattik Tridoshaja*. There was no complain regarding mutra and stool regarding colour or frequency.

Differential Diagnosis

The diagnosis was made on the basis of subjective symptoms and laboratory investigations. Patient’s laboratory finding shown as bellow.

Biochemical		Before treatment	After treatment
Hb%		8.6mg/dl	12.1mg/dl
T.L.C.		3300/cumm	10,700/cumm
DLC	N	55%	68%
	L	41%	30%
	E	1%	2%
	M	2%	0%
	B	0%	0%
ESR		03	06
MCV		66.6 fL	91 FL
MCH		21.5 pg	26 pg
MCHC		32.3 g/dl	32.2 g/dl
Urine test (routine & microscopic)		Normal	Normal
Sr. iron		52 mg/dl	67.21mg/dl
Sr. Bilirubin(T)		0.46mg/dl	0.76mg/dl
SGOT		45 U/L	34.1 U/L
SGPT		21 U/L	41.2 U/L
Sr. urea		10 mg/dl	31.3mg/dl
Sr. creatinine		0.55 mg/dl	0.75mg/dl
Stool examination (ova, cyst)		Normal	Normal

STUDY DESIGN

On the basis of the symptoms, *Darvyadhi Lauha*^{iv}, described in *Rasendra Sara Sangrah* was used as a treatment for the present case. the patient was given the medicine in the dose of 5gm twice a day as *Madhu* and *Ghrit* which are mentioned as *Anupana* of the drug is already present in the drug, thereby increasing the dose of drug. The *Anupana* of drug is luke warm water. The treatment continued for 45 days, and the patient was assessed on the basis of subjective parameter at the interval of 15 days. The subjective assessment was done on the basis of sign and symptoms of *Pandu Roga*. The symptoms were graded as 0,1,2,3 and 4.

Subjective symptoms - The assessment of patient will be done on the basis of improvement in the following symptoms

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|--------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. <i>Panduta</i> | (Pallor) |
| 2. <i>Shrama</i> | (Reduced exercise capacity) |
| 3. <i>Gatrasada</i> | (Fatigue) |
| 4. <i>Shwasa</i> | (Breathlessness) |
| 5. <i>Hridyaspandana</i> | (Palpitation) |
| 6. <i>Aalasya</i> | (Drowsiness) |
| 7. <i>Shiroruja</i> | (Headache) |
| 8. <i>Gatrashoola</i> | (Bodyache) |
| 9. <i>Aruchi</i> | (Anorexia) |
| 10. <i>Dourbalya</i> | (Weakness) |

RESULTS

The assessment done on the 15th, 30th and 45th day of the treatment. In between patient experienced gradual relief in the symptoms. The progress of the patient is given in table 3 in grading format. After treatment, the patient got significant relief in the symptoms.

“A Case Study: Role of *Darvyadi Lauha* in *Pandu Roga*”

Symptoms	Before Treatment	After 15 days	After 30 days	After 45 days
1. <i>Panduta</i>	3	3	2	0
2. <i>Shrama</i>	2	1	1	1
3. <i>Gatrasada</i>	3	2	2	0
4. <i>Shwasa</i>	2	2	1	0
5. <i>Hridyaspandana</i>	2	1	1	0
6. <i>Aalasya</i>	4	3	1	1
7. <i>Shiroruja</i>	1	1	0	0
8. <i>Gatrashoola</i>	0	0	0	0
9. <i>Aruchi</i>	1	1	0	0
10. <i>Dourbalya</i>	3	2	1	1

Grade 0,1,2,3 and 4 represents the none, mild, moderate, moderate to severe and severe state respectively.

DISCUSSION

Darvyadi lauha effects-

- *Darvyadi lauha* contains some medications with *Vatakaphahara* characteristics, while the others are *Tridosha Shamaka*. As a result, it will help to pacify all vitiated *Doshas*. It contains *Anulomana* medicines such as *Haritaki* that aid in the removal of vitiated *Doshas*.
- *Triphala* has *Tridosha Shamaka* qualities. It contains medications such as *Amalaki*, which is high in vitamin C and aids in iron absorption, and *Haritaki*, which has *Anulomana* characteristics and aids in the elimination of vitiated *Doshas* from the body as well as counteracting side effects such as constipation caused by iron compound effects. *Vibhitaki* contains *Chhedana* qualities^{vi}, making it a good *Srotoshodhaka*. Furthermore, because it has *Rasayana* qualities, the *Rasayana* medications will provide appropriate nutrition to the *Dhatu*s, resulting in an increase in *Dhatu*s.
- *Trikatu* has *Deepana*, *Pachana*, and *Srotoshodhana*^{vii} characteristics in *Darvyadi Lauha*, which will raise *Agni* and therefore break the pathogenesis of *Pandu Roga* by working on *AMA*.
- *Shunthi*, *Maricha*, and *Pippali* are *Katu Rasa Pradhana*, and the majority of medications have *Laghu*, *Ruksha*, and *Tikshana Gunas*, which have *Deepana* and *Pachana* qualities. Drugs with *Deepana* and *Pachana* characteristics increase the digestive fire, resulting in improved *Dhatvagni* and *Dhatu Pushti*.
- Worm infestation is closely linked to *Mritika Bhakshana Janya Pandu*, and *Krimighana* drugs such as *Vidanga*^{viii} can help. And *Vidanga* is one of the primary contents in *Darvyadi Lauha*.
- *Daruhaldi* has *Yakritutejaka* property in *Darvyadi Lauha*. *Yakrit* is the *Raktavaha Srotas'* Moola. As a result of its *Yakritutejaka* characteristics, it will boost

Yakrit's ability to create a high-quality and amount of *Rakta Dhatu*.

- Hematinic and hematogenic properties of *Lauha Bhasma*. It comprises a micro-fine particle of highly absorbable elemental iron. *Lauha* has *Rasayana* and *Raktvridhikara* qualities, according to *Ras Ratna Sammucchya*.
- *Madhu* is a potent supplier of iron, copper, and manganese and is *Yogvahi*. *Rasavardhaka*, *Pittahara*, and *Deepana* characteristics of *Ghrita*.

CONCLUSION

Pandu Roga is a fairly frequent disease in society, and adverse effects of allopathic iron preparations, such as constipation and gastrointestinal discomfort, are very common on the basis of above given description about the drug, we can conclude that these drugs increase the bioavailability of *Lauha Bhasma*. *Tridosha Shamaka*, *Yakritutejaka*, *Srotoshodhak*, *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Krimighana*, *Rasayana*, and *Rakta Dhatu Vardhaka* are also features of these medications. These medications have Anti-Inflammatory, Hepatoprotective, Anti-Oxidant, Appetite Stimulant, Anti-Helmenthic and haemoglobin production capabilities, according to contemporary criteria.

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“A Case Study: Role of *Darvyadi Lauha* in *Pandu Roga*”

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